

The Development of a Protocol To Offer Nitrous Oxide in Labor

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Background

- Pain management in labor and delivery is challenging
- Epidural use for complete pain relief is 1st line & intravenous opioids used as an alternative
- No other options for women
- Nitrous oxide (N2O) is widely used in Europe
- The American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology and The American College of Nurse Midwives support the use of N2O

Problem

- Some women have a contraindication or do not want an epidural or opioid medication
- Patients fear effect of epidural or opioids for them and baby
- A 262 licensed-bed community hospital in Anaheim, Ca. does not offer N2O

Purpose

Develop a protocol for N2O as a pain management option for laboring women who are opposed to or have contraindications to epidural anesthesia or intravenous opioid analgesia

Supporting Framework

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Methods

- Protocol development project exempt from IRB – no human subjects
- Priority to address women’s pain in labor identified & confirmed by administration
- Multidisciplinary team was formed & consisted of an Expert Panel who reviewed protocol draft
- The literature reviewed helped in the formation of the protocol
 - Patient eligibility for N2O use
 - contraindications
 - possible adverse effects
 - preparation & administration of N2O
- Protocol finalized after recommendations were included from the Expert Panel
- The Perinatal Patient Safety (PPS) Committee approved protocol
- Since COVID – 19 prevalent, will only offer to women who are screened and COVID negative
- Education of personnel and clinical evaluation of protocol will take place once N2O is obtained

Expert Panel

- Clinical Nurse Specialist with over 10 years’ experience
- Anesthesiologist with over 24 year’s experience
- Certified Nurse Midwife with over 9 year’s experience

Discussion

- Further literature review clarified the use of N2O in preterm labor and patients with a history of asthma. It was contraindicated in severely obese women (BMI >40)
- Although the PPS committee approved the N2O protocol, obtaining N2O was not a priority due to the current pandemic of COVID – 19
- Clinical Nurse Specialist will move forward and contact N2O representative to initiate project, since it may take time to bring it in and educate staff/patients

Conclusions

- Pain is subjective, and each laboring woman experiences pain very differently
- Current literature has shown that N2O is a safe anxiolytic, anesthetic, and analgesic option for women in labor
- The addition of N2O to the pain management options at this community hospital will increase patient satisfaction and decrease anxiety and pain during labor